

Effects of Virgin Coconut Oil on Acetaminophen-Induced Hepatotoxicity in Wistar Rats

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ABSTRACT

Acetaminophen is an extensively used analgesic and antipyretic drug which is most often used without prescription and, its over dose can cause liver damage. This study therefore, investigated the hepatotoxicity of acetaminophen and the protective effects of virgin coconut oil through histological and biochemical procedures using adult Wistar rats. Twenty male rats with an average weight of 200g were randomly assigned into four groups designated 1-4 (n=5). All the rats were exposed to 650mg/kg body weight of acetaminophen daily, in addition rats in group 2 received 5ml/kg body weight of virgin coconut oil (VCO) daily, rats in group 3 received 10ml/kg body weight of VCO and group 4 received 15ml/kg of VCO for fifteen days through orogastric canula administration. While the control rats received distilled water. The rats were fed with Vital® finisher mash, and given water ad libitum. The rats were sacrificed by local anesthesia (chloroform) method on the sixteenth day of the experiment. Blood was collected through cardiac puncture for biochemical analysis of liver enzymes, and livers were excised for histological tissue processing and examination. The values obtained from the test were subjected to analysis of Variance, and mean comparison by Dunnett post hoc test using statistical package for social sciences. The levels of aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alkaline amino transferase (ALT) and alanine phosphatase (ALP) in the test group 1 increased and was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the control group. The enzyme level of AST, ALT, ALP in test group 2 decreased and was statistically insignificant ($P > 0.05$) when compared to test group 1, the enzyme level of AST, ALT, ALP in test group 3 decreased and was statistically insignificant ($P > 0.05$) when compared to test group 1. The results showed moderate damage of liver cells in group 1, mild damage of liver cells in group 2 and no damage of liver cells in group 3 and 4. Therefore virgin coconut oil has protective effect against hepatic injury induced by acetaminophen..

Keywords: Acetaminophen, Virgin Coconut oil, Hepatotoxicity, Liver, Wistar Rats

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INTRODUCTION

Acetaminophen (Paracetamol; APAP) is a common drug that is widely used for the relief of fever, headaches, the pain of arthritis and other minor aches. Paracetamol is safe at therapeutic levels, but an overdose of paracetamol induces liver oxidative stress, hepatotoxicity, liver damage and nephrotoxicity 1,2. Some studies have shown that paracetamol is toxic to the reproductive system, liver, macrophage cells and kidneys when used in high repeated doses 3,4,5,6.

Paracetamol is metabolized by cytochrome P450 to produce N-acetyl-p-benzoquinoneimine (NAPQI), which can react with glutathione (GSH) to result in oxidative stress, and may induce cell injury by damaging the mitochondria 7,8. The Liver is the largest organ in the human body and key organ of metabolism, and performs other functions including glycogen storage, decomposition of red blood cells, plasma protein synthesis, and detoxification³. It is continuously and variedly exposed to xenobiotics and environmental pollutants, because of its strategic placement in the body. The liver is therefore, a vulnerable organ, being exposed to both the parent drug absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract via the portal vein and to any metabolites produced which then enter the systemic circulation via the hepatic vein. If the natural protective mechanisms of the liver are over powered during all such exposures, this will lead to hepatic injury 4.

Hepatotoxicity implies chemical-driven liver damage. It may not be particularly common in general patient populations but the case fatality rate is often high, and the severity of induced hepatic injury is such that drugs are a major cause of hepatic failure¹¹. Several factors, including chemical agents such as those used in the laboratories and industries, natural chemicals (e.g. microcystins) and herbal remedies can induce hepatotoxicity 11. Chemicals that cause liver injury are called hepatotoxins. More than 900 drugs have been implicated in causing liver injury 12. Chemicals often cause subclinical injury to liver which manifests only as

abnormal liver enzyme. Hepatotoxicity is responsible for 5% of all hospital admissions, and 50% of all acute liver failures 12. Drug related hepatotoxicity is an important cause of morbidity and mortality and indeed is the most common reason for withdrawing new drugs 1,2

Virgin Coconut Oil (VCO), the purest form of coconut oil is essentially colourless and free from rancidity. Unlike natural coconut oil, it is endowed with the natural antioxidant Vitamin E, which prevents the peroxidation reaction. VCO mainly consists of Medium Chain Triglycerides (MCT), which are resistant to peroxidation. They differ from animal fat which consists of long chain saturated fatty acids and is the major risk factor for cardiac complication. Medium chain fatty acids (MCFA) differ from long chain fatty acids in that they actually help to protect against heart disease. They have been reported to lower the risk of both atherosclerosis and several other diseases 2. Medium chain fatty acids are reported to be primarily responsible for the special and beneficial effects of VCO 11. The best known dietary sources of MCFA include coconut and palm kernel oils. Various benefits of coconut oil include antiviral, antibacterial, antifungal, antiparasitic, antithrombotic, cardioprotective, hepatoprotective, antidotal, antidermatophytic, antidiabetic, insect repellent, hypolipidemic, anticholelcytic, antioxidant, anticancer, anticaries and disinfectant activities 12. It is also effective in fighting intestinal infections, bronchitis, asthma and headaches 13. It would therefore be worthwhile to examine the protective effects of virgin coconut oil on acetaminophen-induced hepatotoxicity in Wistar rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Health Research Ethics Committee (HREC), College of Health Sciences, Benue State University, Makurdi granted the approval before the commencement of the work. Twenty male Wistar rats with an average weight of 200g were randomly assigned into four groups: (n1=5). The rats

were obtained and maintained in the Animal House of the College of Health Sciences, Benue State University, Makurdi. They were fed with Vital® finisher mash obtained from a dealer at High Level Market, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria and were given water ad libitum. Acetaminophen (Glaxo SmithKline Pharmaceuticals Ltd, United Kingdom) and coconut (cold expressed method) were locally purchased and used for the study. All the rats were exposed to 650mg/kg body weight of acetaminophen once daily for 15 days. In addition, group 2 received 5ml/kg body weight virgin coconut oil, group 3 received 10ml/kg body weight of virgin coconut oil and group 4 received 15ml/kg body weight of virgin coconut oil. Treatment with VCO was once daily for 15 days through orogastric canula. While group 1 that received sterile water served as the negative control. The rats were anaesthetised and sacrificed on the sixteenth day of the experiment and blood was collected for biochemical enzymes studies. The estimation of serum Aspartate transaminase (AST) activity was performed using the AST test kit (Randox Laboratories Ltd, United Kingdom) using the method previously described by Reitman and Frankline (1957), in which the absorbance of the samples were read on a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 405nm with water as blank (10,19). Liver tissues were also excised for histological tissue processing and examination. The values obtained from the control and test groups were recorded and compared statistically using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Histological Analysis; Haematoxylin and Eosin (H & E) stains were used for tissue examination as described by (3, 19).

RESULTS

The micrographs of sectioned liver of Wistar rats exposed to overdose of acetaminophen and treated with virgin coconut oil is shown (plate 1 - 4). Rats in control group showed no histological abnormalities in their liver sections when viewed with light microscope. The sections showed normal arrangements of liver lobules,

central vein, hepatocytes and blood sinusoids (plate 1). Rats in group II had sections showing hepatocytes with intra-cytoplasmic vacuolization, pyknotic nuclei and accumulation of lipid droplets, cloudy swelling, necrosis, expanded and congested blood vessel (plate 2). Rats in group III showed hepatocytes with central and spherical nuclei, portal area with blood vessels and bile duct (plate.3). The sections taken from rats in group IV showed hepatocytes with normal cytoplasm, central and spherical nuclei and blood sinusoids (plate 4)

Plate 1: Light micrograph (x100) of liver sections from rats given sterile water for 15 days. Liver in group 1 showing the normal structure of liver lobules, central vein CV, hepatocytes H, and blood sinusoids S stained with H&E.

Plate 2: Light micrograph (x100) of liver sections from rats given acetaminophen for 15 days. Liver in group 2 showing the hepatocytes with intracytoplasmic vacuolization H, and inflammatory cells I stained with H&E.

Plate 3. Light micrograph (x100) of liver sections from rats given acetaminophen and low dose of virgin coconut oil for 15 days. Liver in group 3 showing the hepatocytes with central nuclei H, Central vein CV, and stained with H&E.

Plate 4: Light micrograph (x100) of liver sections from rats given acetaminophen and high dose of virgin coconut oil for 15 days. Liver in group 4 showing normal central vein CV, blood sinusoid S, stained with H&E.

Biochemical Studies

As shown in figure 1, there were no significant differences ($P < 0.05$) observed for serum AST, ALT, ALP activities in animals treated with VCO compared with the control group. Animals treated with paracetamol only had

significant increase ($P > 0.05$) in the activities of AST, ALT and ALP after 15 days of treatment. Animals treated with paracetamol and VCO had a significantly lower ($P < 0.05$) in AST, ALT and ALP activities when compared to the paracetamol tested group.

Figure 1: Means of biochemical enzymes concentration in control and experimental groups p value < 0.05

DISCUSSION

Normal histological sections of the liver of Wistar rats associated with hepatocytes, central vein and sinusoidal dilatation. Rats that were exposed to showed intracytoplasmic vacuolization of the hepatocytes and inflammatory cells. These changes were observed in most lobules and an indication of toxic effect of acetaminophen, but not as in rats that were untreated. These results corroborate the findings of researcher such as 14 which showed that the major target organ affected by acetaminophen poisoning is the liver, and that the primary lesion is acute centrilobular hepatic necrosis. The observations from the current study are consistent with several studies reporting that higher doses of acetaminophen induce liver damage and hepatotoxicity 14,15. Additionally, other researchers have found that acetaminophen induces oxidative stress via the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS; also known

as free radicals), which play a central role in hepatotoxicity 16.

The histological examination of liver sections from animals given acetaminophen and 5ml/kg of virgin coconut oil showed hepatic degeneration, and the pathological lesions caused by acetaminophen were minimal. Most hepatocytes had a normal appearance with central and spherical nuclei, central vein and blood sinusoids. The virgin coconut oil in the present study showed slight improvement in the histology of most hepatocytes compared to rats given acetaminophen. These results are similar to several studies which have reported that virgin coconut oil may provide full protection against many chemicals and metals that are known to induce hepatotoxicity or liver damage 17.

From the outcome of past researchers, the protective effect of virgin coconut oil may be due to the presence of polyphenolic compounds, which have an antioxidant effect against the toxicity in hepatocytes 16, 17. In addition, it has also been reported that the protective effects of virgin coconut oil against oxidative damage are mainly associated with the nutrigenomic effects of the polyphenol-rich watery (hydrophilic) components on the body's own antioxidant network 18. The polyphenol fraction of virgin coconut oil seems to be effective in reducing toxin-induced oxidative stress.

The examination of liver sections of rats given acetaminophen and high dose of virgin coconut oil showed normal structure of hepatic cords, polygonal hepatocytes with spherical nuclei, a central vein and blood sinusoids. This suggests that virgin coconut oil has no toxicity in the liver, which is in agreement with many similar studies which have reported that virgin coconut oil does not affect the liver tissue, and therefore can be accepted as a safe natural product with no health hazards or significant side effects irrespective of dose taken.

The liver is an important organ that plays vital roles in digestion, metabolism, detoxification and storage of nutrients 1, 20. Hepatic damage often manifests as gross alteration of hepatic architecture, elevation of liver enzymes and alkaline phosphatase and an index to

measure changes in hepatic function. 20

In this study, the liver enzymes and alkaline phosphatase of Wistar rats that were treated with virgin coconut oil on exposure to overdose of acetaminophen were significantly lower compare to the control. This implies that the virgin coconut oil ameliorated the hepatic damaging effects induced by acetaminophen. The result obtained in this study agrees with the findings of Zakaria et al. 12 who reported the hepatoprotective activity of dried and fermented processed virgin coconut oil.

In conclusion, oral administration of virgin coconut oil mitigated acetaminophen-induced hepatic injury in Wistar rats.s.

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